

Quantum gravity and gauge neural network

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The theory of everything is mainly associated with the general theory of relativity and the standard model. On the one hand, the equivalence principle and on the other hand the gauge principle. The two principles are completely opposite to use, one for space-time geometry, the other for quantum fields. For the union is looking for a way called quantum gravity. Canonical quantization of gravity is called Wheeler equation. However, there are difficulties, lack of time and the inability to combine with quantum fields. The equation is purely wave and geometric.

All fundamental laws are usually symmetrical in time, even the gauge fields of the standard model are reversible. However, in the real world, time has a strict direction to the future. This is another problem.

We believe that the quantum gravity equation is not linear in time. This trip is supported by Roger Penrose and Lee Smolin. At the fundamental level on the scale of the Planck, time is real and has an arrow due to the nonlinearity of the quantum gravity equation.

In the recent work we generalized the concept of Cotton Flow is not in the form of a metric, but in the form of a gauge field [1]. This equation describes the behavior of nonlinear in the time of the gauge field on the scale of the Planck.

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = k C$$

$$A_\alpha = \partial_\alpha S$$

$$F_{\alpha\gamma} = \partial_\alpha A_\gamma - A_\alpha A_\gamma$$

$$C = e^{\alpha\beta\gamma} C_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$$

$$C_{\alpha\beta\gamma} = \partial_\alpha F_{\beta\gamma}$$

$$k = \frac{4\pi G\hbar}{c^2}$$

In this equation for the gauge field, the solution itself is interesting in the form of finding the local phase of the wave function.

$$\psi = e^{iS}$$

$$S = S(x, y, z, t)$$

The general solution of the nonlinear equation in time will be

$$S = k \int C dt + \int A^\alpha dx_\alpha + f(x, y, z, t)$$

Consider some solutions for special cases.

With a constant local phase of the wave function.

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = 0$$

$$C = 0$$

Cotton Flow is zero, among its solutions for the gauge field, several models of the distribution of the local phase in space are obtained, the most simple is a cylindrical surface.

As an increase in the time of the local phase of the wave function.

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} > 0$$

$$C > 0$$

Cotton Flow is positive, among its solutions for the gauge field, it turns out in the form of a connection of cylindrical surfaces for the local phase.

With a decrease in the time of the local phase of the wave function.

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} > 0$$

$$C > 0$$

Cotton Flow is negative, among its solutions for the gauge field, a decay in the form of cylindrical surfaces for the local phase is obtained.

Thus, a series of compounds and splitting of cylindrical pipelines together creates a topological structure of a gauge field as a web or in the form of neural networks on the scale of the Planck. The neural network of the gauge field is subject to a nonlinear equation so that it develops in the future and expanded. This neural network is dynamic in time.

In vacuum, only the average field value is observed. Therefore, the average value of potential energy in the form of a scalar function for a nonlinear field is zero

$$\langle \Phi \rangle = \left\langle \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} \right\rangle = 0$$

From here, the field strengths are obtained, without a scalar function

$$\langle \vec{x} \rangle = \vec{\nabla} \langle \Phi \rangle - \frac{\partial \langle \vec{A} \rangle}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \langle \vec{A} \rangle}{\partial t}$$

$$\langle \vec{\eta} \rangle = \vec{\nabla} \times \langle \vec{A} \rangle$$

As a result, the average state of the nonlinear field is invariant with regard to space-time transformations

$$\langle \vec{x} \rangle^2 - c^2 \langle \vec{\eta} \rangle^2 = \langle \vec{x} \rangle^2 - c^2 \langle \vec{\eta} \rangle^2$$

Consequently, there will be no dedicated reference systems for this vacuum state.

Consider other solutions of nonlinear Cotton Flow for the gauge field.

1. Gravity and gauge field scale Planck.

In this chapter, we will show how the gauge neural network on the scale of the Planck creates gravity on a large scale, where there is a classic world.

Consider the equation of the neural field.

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = k C$$

We make an assumption that on a large scale curvature of the field due to the least

$$F_{\alpha\gamma} = \partial_\alpha A_\gamma - A_\alpha A_\gamma \approx A_\alpha A_\gamma$$

$$C \approx e^{\beta\alpha\gamma} A_\beta \partial_\alpha A_\gamma$$

As a result, the gauge equation is obtained with these conditions.

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = k e^{\beta\alpha\gamma} A_\beta \partial_\alpha A_\gamma$$

Can be determined in the form of a function from the local phase

$$A_\alpha = \partial_\alpha S$$

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = k e^{\alpha\beta\gamma} \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_\alpha} \frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial x_\beta \partial x_\gamma}$$

Decision in the form of a reduction in the rule of differentiation of derivatives

$$v_\alpha = \frac{dx_\alpha}{dt} = k e^{\alpha\beta\gamma} \frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial x_\beta \partial x_\gamma}$$

As can be seen, there is some idea of the speed of movement, that is, the initial concept of kinematics.

We introduce the transverse surface in the form of an area

$$d\Omega^\alpha = e^{\alpha\beta\gamma} dx_\beta dx_\gamma$$

As a result, an additional solution for the local phase of the gauge neural field will be

$$S = k \int C dt + \int A^\alpha dx_\alpha + \frac{1}{k} \int v_\alpha d\Omega^\alpha + f(x, y, z, t)$$

The most amazing, the emergence of the foundation is associated with the concept of the movement of inertial reference systems in the form of kinematics of the surface frame. This global symmetry creates the relativity of motion. Nonlinear gauge neural network already has an initial idea of moving kinematics. Moreover, now we will see the appearance of gravity.

Consider the kinematic action for the gauge neural network

$$S = \frac{1}{k} \int v_\alpha d\Omega^\alpha$$

Let the reference system accelerates

$$v_\alpha = \int a_\alpha dt$$

Then the action will be accelerated

$$S = \frac{1}{k} \int a_\alpha d\Omega^\alpha dt$$

This definition of action in the form of a function of time, besides, if there is matter in this gauge neural network, the overall action will be

$$S \rightarrow \frac{c^2}{4\pi G} \int a_\alpha d\Omega^\alpha dt + \int Mc^2 dt$$

As a result, when variations are obtained, the Gauss theorem is obtained for the source of the gravitational field.

$$\oint a_\alpha d\Omega^\alpha = -4\pi GM = - \int \rho dV$$

Thus, we have the Poisson equation for the gravitational field, which is true in the classical world, when taking into account the signal transmission limit at the speed of light the theory of gravity is described by the general theory relativity. Gravity is a curvature of space-time. On the other hand, our theory also describes gravity as a dynamic state of the gauge neural network. Thus, the source quantum state of space-time is like a neutron network on a scale Planck based on a gauge principle. In fact, quantum gravity is a non-linear quantum field theory on the scale of the Planck.

What does it mean? The curvature and dynamics of space can be viewed as the dynamics of a nonlinear neural gauge network.

Consider the kinematic part of the action

$$S = \frac{1}{k} \int v_\alpha d\Omega^\alpha = \frac{1}{k} \frac{dV}{dt}$$

Expansion or compression of space define through the speed of change of volume and metric

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = \dot{e} V$$

$$H = \frac{\dot{e}}{e}$$

As a result, the action for the dynamics of space gives a non-commutative bracket

$$S = \frac{1}{k} \int v_\alpha d\Omega^\alpha = \frac{1}{k} e H V$$

$$\{e, H\} = i \frac{k}{V}$$

This is the basic ratio for quantum cosmology, which is based on the Wheeler - de Witt equation for the geometry of space. If more general metric concepts are replaced.

$$e \rightarrow \gamma_{ik} \quad H \rightarrow \pi_{ik}$$

$$\gamma^{ik\alpha\beta} \pi_{ik} \pi_{\alpha\beta} + \sqrt{\gamma} R = 0$$

However, in the Wheeler -de Witt equation, there is no time, this quantum universe is frozen. In our model for the gauge neutral network, the nonlinear Cotton Flow equation is used, which contains the time, but also recognizes the time boom on the fundamental level. In addition, this equation combines gravity with quantum gauge fields. Hence the investigation of our work, quantum gravity is a nonlinear quantum field theory without a metric description on the scale Planck.

[1] Quantum Cotton flow in spin network, Kuyukov V., osf.preprints, 2020.

[2] A.U.O Kisil, O.Sarioglu and B.Tekin, Cotton flow, Class.Quant.Grav.25, 165019 (2008).